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Research Article

**ELECTIVE LAPAROSCOPY IN DIAGNOSING CHRONIC
ABDOMINAL PAIN**¹ Dr. Agha Taj Muhammad, ²Dr. Kelash Kumar, ¹Dr. Dr. Salma Kadir,
³Dr. Asim Munir Memon, ^{3*}Dr. Samar Raza, ³Dr. Vijay Kumar¹Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS) Jamshoro²Associate Consultant, Indus Hospital Badin Campus³Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad / Jamshoro**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the elective laparoscopy in diagnosing chronic abdominal pain.**Patients And Methods:** The one year cross sectional study (2017-18) was conducted at tertiary care hospital on the patients present with pain abdomen of 3 months duration or more. A detailed history was taken from each of the patient as per the proforma designed before the commencement of the study whereas the frequency / percentages (%) and means \pm SD computed for study variables. All cases of undiagnosed (by conventional methods and investigations such as detailed history, clinical examination, blood counts, urine examination, USG abdomen, Plain x ray abdomen) chronic abdominal pain > 3 months duration of both sex, all cases of undiagnosed chronic abdominal pain in patients > 12 years of age and cases of clinically diagnosed chronic abdominal pain of >3 months duration not responding to the treatment given were placed in inclusion criteria whereas the frequency / percentages (%) and means \pm SD computed for study variables.**Results:** During one year study period total fifty patients were explored and study. The mean \pm SD for age (yrs) of population was 52.21 ± 7.72 . The laparoscopic findings were post operative adhesions 28 (56%), recurrent appendicitis 08 (16%), chronic cholecystitis 02 (4.0%), malignancy 04 (8.0%), mesenteric lymphadenopathy 04 (8.0%), tuberculosis (strictures) 04 (8.0%).**Conclusion:** Laparoscopy has an effective diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic efficacy in the management of patients who present with chronic abdominal pain and conventional methods of investigations have failed to elicit a cause for the pain.**Keywords:** Pain, laparoscopy, abdomen**Corresponding author:*****Dr. Samar Raza,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Patients with chronic abdominal pain are amongst the most difficult to manage. Potentially it can be unrewarding for both the patient and the treating physician. Chronic abdominal pain is a difficult complaint. It leads to evident suffering and disability, both physically and psychologically [1]. Chronic abdominal pain is associated with poor quality of life. Studies conducted with large community samples or hospital populations imply chronic abdominal pain is a pervasive problem. Most patients in this group would have already undergone many diagnostic procedures [2, 3]. More than 40% of the patients presenting with chronic abdominal pain have no specific etiological diagnosis at the end of their diagnostic workup. These searches for pathology often include such procedures as upper and lower gastrointestinal endoscopies, computerized tomography and screening for undetected carcinoma. Diagnostic laparoscopy can be done under direct vision with simple equipment as it does not require a video camera or the electronic gadgetry associated with laparoscopic surgery. With advances in optics, laparoscopy allows perfect visual examination of the peritoneal cavity and further makes possible histological diagnosis of target biopsy under vision [4]. Laparoscopy is as much a surgical procedure as an exploratory laparotomy, often just as informative, and to the trained surgeon affords a better view of the entire peritoneal cavity than the usual exploratory laparotomy. In many cases it prevents unnecessary/negative laparotomy. The rapid recovery and return to normal activity that follow diagnostic laparoscopic surgery provide an extra incentive for the surgeon to adopt more laparoscopic techniques.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The one year cross sectional study (2017-2018) was conducted at tertiary care hospital on the patients present with pain abdomen of 3 months duration or more. A detailed history was taken from each of the patient as per the proforma designed before the commencement of the study.

The clinical examination findings were also recorded in the proforma. The recorded data included particulars of the patient, duration of illness, site of abdominal pain, other associated symptoms such as vomiting or fever or white discharge per vagina, past history of surgical explorations, co morbid conditions, investigations. Subsequently the intra operative findings, therapeutic/ diagnostic intervention done, correlation of the intra operative findings with the histopathology report, complications during the intra and post operative period and the relief from the pain were recorded and analyzed. As a part of the work up of a patient the routine baseline investigations were done. All cases of undiagnosed (by conventional methods and investigations such as detailed history, clinical examination, blood counts, urine examination, USG abdomen, Plain x ray abdomen) chronic abdominal pain >3months duration of both sex, all cases of undiagnosed chronic abdominal pain in patients > 12years of age and cases of clinically diagnosed chronic abdominal pain of >3 months duration not responding to the treatment given were placed in inclusion criteria while All cases of undiagnosed chronic abdominal pain <3months duration of both gender and all cases of undiagnosed chronic abdominal pain in patients <12years of age were placed in exclusion criteria while all surgeries were carried out under general anesthesia. The surgical procedure carried out were depending on the intra operative findings and as per indications which ranged from biopsy from suspicious lesions to adhesiolysis to appendectomy while the data was collected on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS:

During one year study period total fifty patients were explored and study. The mean \pm SD for age (yrs) of population was 52.21 ± 7.72 . The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
30-39	10	20
40-49	20	40
50-59	12	24
60-70	05	10
70+	03	6.0
GENDER		
Male	30	60
Female	20	40
RESIDENCE		
Urban	30	60
Rural	20	40
DURATION OF PAIN (months)		
3-12	08	16
12-18	14	28
18-36	16	32
>36	12	24
REGION		
Upper abdomen	08	16
Peri umbilical	20	40
Lower abdomen	06	12
Diffuse abdomen	16	32
LAPAROSCOPIC FINDINGS		
Post operative adhesions	28	56
Recurrent Appendicitis	08	16
Chronic Cholecystitis	02	4.0
Malignancy	04	8.0
Mesenteric Lymphadenopathy	04	8.0
Tuberculosis (strictures)	04	8.0

DISCUSSION:

Chronic abdominal pain is a common problem dealt not only by the general surgeon but by all practicing physicians. Even after extensive non-invasive work up of such patients, the exact cause of pain abdomen is seldom known. The aim of our study was to study the efficacy of diagnostic laparoscopy as an investigative and therapeutic modality in the diagnosis and management of patients with chronic pain abdomen. Diagnostic laparoscopy makes it possible for the surgeon to directly visualize the contents of the abdominal cavity better than any other investigative modality. The study confirmed that in this difficult patient group, laparoscopy could safely identify abnormal findings and can improve the outcome in a majority of the cases. In a study by Raymond P, et al [5] for utility of laparoscopy in chronic abdominal pain involving 70 patients, the average age was 42 years. In a study by Gouda M El- Labban and

Emad N Hokkam [4] involving 30 patients, the average age of presentation was 36 years. In a study by Gouda M El-labban [6] involving 30 patients, the duration of pain ranged from 3 to 15 months. Lavonius M et al [7] in their study of laparoscopy for chronic abdominal pain in 46 patients reported post operative adhesions in 63% of case. Laparoscopy is a useful technique for the diagnosis and treatment of abdominal pain even if the appendix is normal on inspection [8]. Therapeutic efficacy here denotes the percentage of patients who reported a positive outcome (no pain or decrease in pain) at the time of follow up. The efficacy of diagnostic laparoscopy achieved in the present study compares well with former literature [9].

CONCLUSION:

Laparoscopy has an effective diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic efficacy in the management of

patients who present with chronic abdominal pain and conventional methods of investigations have failed to elicit a cause for the pain. So it is safe, quick and effective modality of investigation for chronic abdominal pain while has a high diagnostic and therapeutic efficacy.

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